
**FACTORS AFFECTING STRATEGIC PLANNING AND MANAGEMENT OF
PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS: A META ANALYSIS APPROACH**

**A Research
Presented to the
Faculty of Graduate School
St. Paul University Philippines
Tuguegarao City, Cagayan**

**In partial fulfilment
Of the requirements for the course
Strategic Planning and Management**

**by
KRISTOFFER PAULO L. RAMIREZ
Ph.D in Mathematics Education
September 2019**

INTRODUCTION

A strategic plan helps to provide direction and focus for all employees. Management needs a well-developed strategic plan in order to effectively establish expectations for their organization. Without a plan, expectations are developed in a void and there is little or no alignment with organizational goals. Bryson (2000) defined strategic planning as an organization process of defining strategy or direction and making decisions on allocating resources to pursue the strategy. The strength of the entire process of strategic planning is tested by the efficacy of the strategy finally forged by the organization. To deliver the best results, strategic planning requires broad yet effective information gathering, development and exploration of strategic alternatives, and an emphasis on future implications of present decisions.

Strategic planning has been characterized by its increased emphasis on implementation, its flexibility and adaptability to the ever changing environment, its ability to focus on identifying key issues and its ability to enhance strategic thinking.

The Education Sector Strategic Plan (ESSP 2010-2015) identified the following as benefits of strategic planning; enables stakeholders to establish clear priorities, encourage innovation and creativity, helps in co-ordination and provides efficiency in operations of an organization. Due to its many benefits, strategic planning has been embraced in the education sector in very many countries.

OBJECTIVES:

The purpose of this meta-analysis approach is to determine the different factors that may affect the strategic planning and management especially in public secondary schools.

BODY

1. Management commitment

Management commitment had a significant relationship with implementation of strategic plans in public secondary schools. School leadership therefore plays a critical role in the implementation of strategic plans and their commitment is very critical in the success of the entire process. (Okendo, 2018)

As such, effective strategic plan implementation for any organization should include full and active executive

support, effective communication, employee involvement, thorough organizational planning and competitive analysis, and widespread perceived need for strategic planning (Heathfield, 2002)

The leader of an institution must be actively involved in the implementation process for it to be successful. Research also indicates that strategic plans are most successfully implemented in institutions that have clear hierarchical style and bureaucratic structure. In these kinds of organizations decisions are made by the top level managers because power rests with them. For successful implementation of strategic plans, the top managers do not only direct and involve, but also communicate their decisions with the middle level managers in order to win their support (Wooldridge & Floyd, 1990).

2. Teachers commitment

There is a significant positive relationship between teacher commitment and implementation of strategic plans in public secondary schools. There is need therefore to encourage teachers through intrinsic and extrinsic motivation to be totally committed in the formulation,

implementation and evaluation of strategic plans in their schools. (Okendo, 2018)

Having clear procedures, rules and responsibilities enhances the implementation of strategic plans. This is because it increases efficiency and decreases cost of coordination, hence, lowering administrative costs.

When teachers are effectively trained on strategic planning, they will facilitate a proper strategic plans implementation practice since they are normally given the duties to monitor the whole exercise by the school heads thus the study concludes that training should be vital so as to ensure effective strategic plans implementation (Owino, 2015)

3. Community engagement

Accordingly, understanding on various stakeholders and their potential value is the first step toward an effective community engagement strategy. Importantly, engagement efforts must be explicit, and individual board members must be held accountable for developing relationships (Weihrich and Koontz, 1993). Knight (1997) emphasize that community engagement must be intentional, strategic, and sustained over time.

4. Availability of resources

Availability of resources affects the implementation of strategic plans in public secondary schools. Thus availability of organizational resources such as financial, physical and human resources will positively foster implementation of strategic plans (Okendo, 2018).

According to Rumelt (2011), resources are a major prop in strategic plan implementation as they dictate what an organization intends to do and how to do it. There is thus a close connection between strategic plan implementation and the available resources.

Various scholars have classified resources in various categories. According to Fry et. al (2004) ,resources include physical materials, financial assets, technologies, people and information. Lee (2009) on the other hand classified resources into six types which included human, administrative, physical, financial, reputation and political resources.

The study ascertained that resource variation on strategic planning implementation during strategic plans implementation practice was achieved since school managers had the skills from the training on use of finances and

other resources for effective strategic planning of schools. (Owino, 2015)

5. School culture

Hill et al (2009) asserts that institutions culture controls the way members interact with each other and with stakeholders within and without an institution. Culture is one of the strongest elements of control in an institution and it enhances integration, as well as, coordination within the institution. Culture does not only give institutional members ability to develop a collective identity but also guides them in relationships, communication, decision making and in their daily relationships (Buil, 2010).

Additionally, strong cultures encourage successful implementation of strategic plans while weak cultures are a stumbling block. Strong cultures support shared beliefs in norms, practices and virtues within an institution that help strengthen everyone's resolve to carry out their different roles in strategic plan implementation.

6. Managerial skills

To effectively coordinate planned activities and realize effective implementation of a strategic plan, a manager needs technical skills, human skills and conceptual

skills. Technical skills refer to the knowledge and proficiency in trade. These are the skills that a manager needs in order to accomplish a specific task.

Most employees expect that their managers have technical skills that set them above their own so that they can refer to them when need be. In order to effectively spear head strategic plan implementation, the top level management needs technical skills (Pagon, et al. 2008).

However, some leaders would not easily embrace change and competition as part of managerial skills. This would further impact on the extent to which administrators determine relevant strategic management skills. Another 25% of the heads who responded wanted to suggest that some leadership styles avoid supervision which results in lack of implementation of strategies accordingly.

Robbins and Coulter (2012) advocated strategic leadership as the best. Strategic leadership is a family of skills which embrace strategic management issues.

7. Organizational structure

Organizational structures are considered to be positively influencing strategic management skills. If strategic management in a way is promoted by team work and

collaborative tendencies, then in a way organizational structures must impact on the relevant skills.

However, organizational structures for government secondary schools are characterized by bureaucracy at highest levels. In 100% of the structures observed in government secondary schools' notice boards in deputy heads' offices, there is emphasis on protocol. In a way protocol is detrimental to strategic management as it delays progress. To a greater extent, it promotes centralisation of authority.

8. Policies

Borgeirsdottir (2012) indicate that when policies are imposed, a gap often remains between policy and practice. In other words they have little influence on altering the policies. Otherwise, they have to make do with balancing the two. Furthermore, it appears the survival of school-level policies is highly depended on higher level policies.

CONCLUSION

There are many factors that may affect the strategic planning and implementation of the public secondary schools. Availability of resources greatly affects the implementation of strategic plans. Lack of personnel with appropriate

skills is a major challenge to the implementation process. Besides, most of the human resources are not trained on strategic planning. Lack of finances is another hindrance to the implementation process. Due to these challenges, the implementation process is not completed at the scheduled time. The study revealed that the school culture affects implementation of strategic plans. Schools do not operate in a value-free vacuum.

Further, their operations are governed and directed by the school culture. Implementation of strategic plans triggers a cultural change and whether the implementation process will be successful or not depends on how well the stakeholders are prepared for the change. The management and control of the implementation process is done by top level managers and this enhances the implementation process.

RECOMMENDATION

1. Management should provide a leadership role in ensuring that all the stakeholders are committed towards implementing the strategic plans. Their commitment is very paramount because employees will always rely on them since they are under their directives. The management

- should put in clear measures that ensure monitoring and evaluation of strategic plans in their schools.
2. The study also recommends involvement of all stakeholders in the formulation and implementation of strategic plans. Encouraging people to participate and involving them the formulation and implementation of strategic plans will make them own the process and also reduce resistance to change. This implies a persistent mutual trust
 3. The management should design a reward structure to enable the teachers increase levels of commitment on the implementation of strategic plans in the schools. The BOM should initiate strategies of encouraging all stakeholders to the school strategic plans and to the process of implementation. The study recommends that the management of public secondary schools invests time and money in capacity building of all the employees involved in the implementation of the strategic plans in order to expand their skills.
 4. The study also recommends that school principals, deputy principals, heads of departments, teachers and management should be equipped with the necessary managerial skills. This can be academic, technical and conceptual skills to

- help them successfully implement strategic plans in their respective schools. This should be designed to be practical and inclusive to specific regional and geographical conditions of given areas.
5. Resources should be available on time and the BOM should allocate these resources based on the objectives of strategic plans. Schools should have resource allocation policies and budgets which they should enforce strictly to ensure they help in the successful implementation of the school's strategic plans. Based on the findings, the study recommends that adequate provision of resources for the implementation of strategic plans be available as the implementation process is an expensive exercise which ought to be deliberately budgeted for.
 6. Furthermore, there should be effective change management in order to reduce resistance to the change triggered by the implementation of strategic plans. For public schools to improve on strategic plan implementation there is a need to align the school culture to the strategic plan. The managers need to look for ways to encourage employees to adjust their values and beliefs towards the school. It is also upon the managers to come up with ways of addressing

issues of culture lest they hinder the implementation process as most schools do not have a culture of embracing new ideas. Schools also do not have a culture of risk taking.

REFERENCES

Cook, W. J., (1995). Strategic planning in American Schools. (2nd Ed.) Newyork: Arlington Cambridge group. [2].

Dan, A. H. (2013). Determinant of Implementation of Strategic Plans In public Secondary School: A case of Nakuru Sub-County, Kenya, International Journal of Innovative Research & Development:

Eshiwani, G., (1993). Education in Kenya since independence, Nairobi, East African educational publishers.

Finlay, P., (2000). Strategy Management. An Introduction to Business and Corporate Strategy. London: Pearson Education Limited.

Gongera, G., (2000). Strategic Management Institute of Open Learning. Nairobi: Kenyatta University.

Katsioloudes M.(2002) Global strategic planning cultural perspective for profit and non-profit organizations. Butterworth: Heinmann.

Steiner, G.A., (1975). Strategic Planning: What Every Manager Should Know. Free Press.